

Fig.1. Bar Plot by *Structure* 2.3.4., built from the database of Dan Dediu. "A Bayesian phylogenetic approach to estimating the stability of linguistic features and the genetic biasing of tone." *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences* (2010), Electronic supplementary material: rspb20101595, 14-19. K = 20.

Falush, Daniel, Matthew Stephens, and Jonathan K. Pritchard. "Inference of population structure using multilocus genotype data: linked loci and correlated allele frequencies." *Genetics* 164.4 (2003): 1567-1587.

Pritchard, Jonathan K., Matthew Stephens, and Peter Donnelly. "Inference of population structure using multilocus genotype data." *Genetics* 155.2 (2000): 945-959.

17 0.2354 0.1819 0.3028 0.2388 0.2304 0.1259 0.1572 0.2295 0.3031 0.2591 0.2056 0.2959 0.1682 0.2606 0.1968 0.2863 - 0.1652 0.1814 0.1766
 18 0.0540 0.0046 0.0835 0.0880 0.1200 0.0772 0.0063 0.0640 0.1097 0.0896 0.1283 0.1016 0.1031 0.0982 0.0172 0.1029 0.1652 - 0.0896 0.0051
 19 0.1154 0.0984 0.1947 0.2056 0.2121 0.1264 0.0884 0.1602 0.2184 0.2078 0.1277 0.2344 0.1748 0.1569 0.1261 0.2010 0.1814 0.0896 - 0.1087
 20 0.0591 0.0097 0.0742 0.0823 0.1185 0.0849 0.0083 0.0635 0.0939 0.0823 0.1396 0.0828 0.1046 0.1139 0.0062 0.0988 0.1766 0.0051 0.1087 -

Average distances (expected heterozygosity) between individuals in same cluster:

cluster 1 : 0.3058
 cluster 2 : 0.3497
 cluster 3 : 0.2376
 cluster 4 : 0.1876
 cluster 5 : 0.1617
 cluster 6 : 0.1917
 cluster 7 : 0.3771
 cluster 8 : 0.2822
 cluster 9 : 0.2170
 cluster 10 : 0.2331
 cluster 11 : 0.1791
 cluster 12 : 0.2469
 cluster 13 : 0.1351
 cluster 14 : 0.2271
 cluster 15 : 0.3632
 cluster 16 : 0.1483
 cluster 17 : 0.0998
 cluster 18 : 0.3773
 cluster 19 : 0.2643
 cluster 20 : 0.3789

 Estimated Ln Prob of Data = -6734.1
 Mean value of ln likelihood = -4993.3
 Variance of ln likelihood = 3481.6
 Mean value of alpha = 0.0405

Mean value of Fst_1 = 0.4300
 Mean value of Fst_2 = 0.4714
 Mean value of Fst_3 = 0.5472
 Mean value of Fst_4 = 0.6490
 Mean value of Fst_5 = 0.6405
 Mean value of Fst_6 = 0.7174
 Mean value of Fst_7 = 0.3877
 Mean value of Fst_8 = 0.4756
 Mean value of Fst_9 = 0.5897
 Mean value of Fst_10 = 0.7040
 Mean value of Fst_11 = 0.7540
 Mean value of Fst_12 = 0.6258
 Mean value of Fst_13 = 0.7405
 Mean value of Fst_14 = 0.5343
 Mean value of Fst_15 = 0.4821
 Mean value of Fst_16 = 0.7350
 Mean value of Fst_17 = 0.8815
 Mean value of Fst_18 = 0.3530
 Mean value of Fst_19 = 0.6180
 Mean value of Fst_20 = 0.4116

Inferred ancestry of individuals:

Label (%Miss) : Inferred clusters

1 AFRO_ASIATI (31) : 0.013 0.014 0.006 0.009 0.019 0.472 0.031 0.006 0.009 0.098 0.017 0.010 0.026 0.005 0.009 0.040 0.017 0.019 0.154 0.027

234 SINO_TIBETA (36) : 0.004 0.013 0.004 0.605 0.004 0.014 0.010 0.003 0.005 0.003 0.010 0.003 0.016 0.008 0.003 0.005 0.264 0.008 0.014 0.005
235 SINO_TIBETA (32) : 0.002 0.004 0.003 0.899 0.003 0.003 0.008 0.003 0.004 0.003 0.008 0.010 0.004 0.003 0.005 0.003 0.013 0.006 0.007 0.008
236 SINO_TIBETA (38) : 0.003 0.016 0.004 0.710 0.026 0.006 0.016 0.004 0.014 0.040 0.005 0.015 0.078 0.005 0.008 0.006 0.007 0.014 0.007 0.016
237 SINO_TIBETA (58) : 0.123 0.029 0.014 0.012 0.006 0.086 0.050 0.012 0.006 0.006 0.014 0.009 0.159 0.039 0.025 0.019 0.061 0.028 0.275 0.027
238 SINO_TIBETA (9) : 0.005 0.023 0.008 0.262 0.035 0.025 0.087 0.024 0.035 0.032 0.036 0.023 0.040 0.004 0.080 0.010 0.007 0.116 0.008 0.142
239 SINO_TIBETA (11) : 0.004 0.009 0.008 0.809 0.002 0.028 0.017 0.009 0.005 0.005 0.007 0.003 0.023 0.009 0.006 0.005 0.017 0.008 0.016 0.009
240 SINO_TIBETA (51) : 0.014 0.037 0.009 0.115 0.006 0.395 0.053 0.014 0.024 0.005 0.040 0.008 0.044 0.064 0.028 0.012 0.022 0.026 0.056 0.028
241 SINO_TIBETA (59) : 0.047 0.087 0.011 0.062 0.008 0.038 0.131 0.010 0.107 0.032 0.004 0.014 0.120 0.006 0.141 0.005 0.013 0.046 0.009 0.108
242 SINO_TIBETA (54) : 0.015 0.047 0.031 0.186 0.008 0.240 0.089 0.010 0.022 0.011 0.011 0.023 0.013 0.026 0.052 0.035 0.009 0.038 0.081 0.053
243 URALIC_fin (3) : 0.047 0.018 0.011 0.013 0.062 0.008 0.043 0.061 0.019 0.025 0.008 0.005 0.485 0.035 0.035 0.003 0.003 0.060 0.004 0.056
244 URALIC_hun (9) : 0.009 0.012 0.008 0.014 0.086 0.039 0.031 0.018 0.025 0.137 0.016 0.009 0.310 0.007 0.018 0.003 0.004 0.078 0.112 0.064
245 URALIC_kty (52) : 0.084 0.143 0.047 0.028 0.008 0.068 0.153 0.025 0.008 0.007 0.008 0.008 0.058 0.053 0.139 0.010 0.011 0.064 0.020 0.058
246 URALIC_kzy (59) : 0.011 0.012 0.004 0.030 0.504 0.038 0.017 0.010 0.008 0.030 0.026 0.012 0.167 0.006 0.011 0.008 0.044 0.026 0.010 0.026
247 URALIC_nen (25) : 0.020 0.038 0.015 0.007 0.015 0.258 0.033 0.029 0.007 0.057 0.074 0.015 0.131 0.026 0.027 0.050 0.065 0.054 0.044 0.037
248 URALIC_skp (59) : 0.065 0.028 0.052 0.008 0.006 0.012 0.073 0.013 0.010 0.006 0.012 0.004 0.515 0.013 0.062 0.003 0.012 0.036 0.027 0.042
249 UTO_AZTECAN (32) : 0.013 0.029 0.007 0.014 0.003 0.016 0.046 0.005 0.006 0.003 0.165 0.003 0.054 0.204 0.026 0.003 0.025 0.017 0.338 0.022
250 UTO_AZTECAN (23) : 0.251 0.077 0.053 0.014 0.005 0.013 0.209 0.007 0.005 0.004 0.018 0.003 0.014 0.029 0.114 0.004 0.016 0.028 0.068 0.067
251 UTO_AZTECAN (51) : 0.046 0.043 0.012 0.011 0.007 0.022 0.139 0.006 0.005 0.007 0.014 0.004 0.273 0.005 0.088 0.004 0.015 0.034 0.212 0.053
252 UTO_AZTECAN (30) : 0.338 0.022 0.041 0.002 0.036 0.005 0.033 0.388 0.014 0.006 0.011 0.003 0.006 0.006 0.015 0.003 0.003 0.047 0.015 0.006
253 UTO_AZTECAN (47) : 0.013 0.020 0.017 0.007 0.381 0.032 0.032 0.079 0.010 0.018 0.207 0.004 0.066 0.016 0.015 0.007 0.009 0.029 0.010 0.028
254 UTO_AZTECAN (53) : 0.017 0.016 0.036 0.004 0.079 0.008 0.015 0.027 0.004 0.255 0.413 0.008 0.007 0.005 0.011 0.040 0.005 0.021 0.009 0.018
255 UTO_AZTECAN (8) : 0.049 0.116 0.008 0.082 0.015 0.049 0.223 0.029 0.013 0.005 0.005 0.006 0.043 0.011 0.101 0.004 0.013 0.063 0.068 0.096

Figure 2: likelihood values across multiple values of K produced by STRUCTURE HARVESTER.

Earl, Dent A. and vonHold, Bridgett. "STRUCTURE HARVESTER: a website and program for visualizing STRUCTURE output and implementing the Evanno method." *Conservation genetics resources* 4.2 (2012): 359-361.

Figure 3. Tree produced by MrBayes. I exclude from the corpus each language with greater than 30% data which refer to acculturation signal and blur the phylogenetic signal (Greenhill and al. 2009). The longest branche was chosen as outgroup. Retention Index: 0.75.

A similar method has been used by Bowers 2012 on a more local level and by d'Huy 2015 who used it to study the cultural structure of folktales on a global level.

set autoclose=yes nowarn=yes; lset nst=6 rates=invgamma; unlink statefreq=(all) revmat=(all) shape=(all) pinvar=(all); prset applyto=(all) ratepr=variable; mcmc ngen= 80000000 relburnin=yes burninfrac=0.25 printfreq=10000 samplefreq=10000 nchains=4 savebrlens=yes; mcmc;

Bowern, Claire. "The riddle of Tasmanian languages." *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences* 279.1747 (2012): 4590-4595.

Greenhill, Simon J., Thomas E. Currie, and Russell D. Gray. "Does horizontal transmission invalidate cultural phylogenies?" *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences* 276.1665 (2009): 2299-2306.

Huelsenbeck, John P., and Fredrik Ronquist. "MRBAYES: Bayesian inference of phylogenetic trees." *Bioinformatics* 17.8 (2001): 754-755.

d'Huy, Julien, "Une nouvelle méthode, rapide et efficace, pour reconstruire les premières migrations de l'humanité." *Mythologie française*, 259 (2015): 66-82.

Maddison, W.P. and D.R. Maddison. 2011. *Mesquite: a Modular System for Evolutionary Analysis*. Version 2.75.

Ronquist, Fredrik, and John P. Huelsenbeck. "MrBayes 3: Bayesian phylogenetic inference under mixed models." *Bioinformatics* 19.12 (2003): 1572-1574.

Figure 4. Neighbor-joining tree (Distance: Uncorrected_P) by Splitstree4.

Huson, Daniel H., and David Bryant. "Application of phylogenetic networks in evolutionary studies." *Molecular biology and evolution* 23.2 (2006): 254-267.

Figure 5. NeighborNet graph estimated from p-distances with SplitsTree4, to compare with the results of Gray, Russell D., David Bryant, and Simon J. Greenhill. "On the shape and fabric of human history." *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 365.1559 (2010): 3923-3933.

Delta score = 0.3941
Q-residual score = 0.08549

Huson, Daniel H., and David Bryant. "Application of phylogenetic networks in evolutionary studies." *Molecular biology and evolution* 23.2 (2006): 254-267.